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PHOENIX

Nanomedicine for organ transplant tolerance

D5.5: Updated Data Management Plan

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PHOENIX Consortium

Full Name	Short Name	Beneficiary Number	Role
ISTITUTO DIRICERCHE FARMACOLOGICHE MARIO NEGRI	IRFMN	1	Coordinator
FUNDACIO CLINIC PER A LA RECERCA BIOMEDICA	FCRB	2	Beneficiary
CENTRE HOSPITALIER UNIVERSITAIRE DE RENNES	CHUR	3	Beneficiary
PINTAIL LTD	PT	4	Beneficiary
INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE POUR L'AGRICULTURE, L'ALIMENTATION ET L'ENVIRONNEMENT	INRAE	5	Beneficiary

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V0.4	Updated DRAFT	17.07.2024
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D5.5 Updated Data Management Plan

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1. Executive Summary

Deliverable D5.5 - *Updated Data Management Plan* (DMP) reviews and updates *D5.3 – Initial Data Management Plan*, as the formal statement describing how research data will be managed and documented throughout the research project and the terms regarding the subsequent deposit of the data with a data repository for long-term management and preservation.

Beneficiary Pintail is responsible for D5.5 as part of Work Package 5 (WP5) which has four objectives (refer below) and is broadly responsible for Management, Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation.

Since the D5.3 was submitted, an additional beneficiary (Beneficiary #5, INRAE) has joined the PHOENIX project, via Amendment (AMD-101076383-4). One of the key updates to the DMP is thus the incorporation of INRAE into the DMP; further, the initial DMP has been reviewed by all other beneficiaries to ensure it remains up to date and accurate.

PHOENIX is developing and validating a new immunotherapy for transplant medicine that prevents graft rejection and induces transplant tolerance, without compromising normal immunity to infections and cancer. PHOENIX aims to pre-clinically validate this new approach in transplants of two organs (kidney and liver) in two animal species (mice and pigs), to provide robust evidence for future clinical trials.

A *new* data output of PHOENIX will be shared experimental data, including laboratory research (phenotype, immunological function, transcriptomic, sex, weight, age, etc.) data collected in our planned murine and porcine studies and analysed in PHOENIX to assess the efficacy of the new nanomedicines. PHOENIX will also produce data such as specifications for the pMHC-NP nanoparticle production, experimental protocols, and single cell transcriptomic data. Data will be prepared and submitted in a form to facilitate re-use, complying entirely with the FAIR principles.

PHOENIX will also *re-use* data, comparing PHOENIX data for example with existing datasets in Single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNAseq) from previous research.

As required by Article 17 of the Grant Agreement, the PHOENIX Data Management Plan (DMP) adheres to the FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability). It outlines the management of data through the aspects of the lifecycle of research outputs, namely the provenance, organisation and curation of, and access to, data, during and post project.

The DMP is a living document that will be updated during the PHOENIX project by beneficiaries when a significant change in relation to data arises. In line with best practice, D5.3 and D5.5 are both classified as non-restricted, public deliverables.

2. Introduction and Background

Organ transplant medicine is currently limited by life-long immunosuppression and vulnerability to infections, malignancies and cardiovascular diseases. Further, there is a 20% rate of long-term graft failure. The PHOENIX project addresses this challenge, by reprogramming the local immune micro-

environment around a graft organ, inducing long-term transplant tolerance without broader systemic immunosuppression.

In PHOENIX, the team are designing and building a unique nanomedicine which delivers ubiquitous or self-antigens - common to all humans – that will redirect the host immune response against the graft toward regulation and tolerance development. These medicines will be demonstrated in murine and porcine models, laying the foundation for human clinical trials immediately post-project. The research conducted in PHOENIX will deliver new data, this is described in detail in section 4.1 below.

In this project, Work Package 5 Communications, Dissemination, Exploitation and Management (WP5) is led by beneficiaries Istituto Di Ricerche Farmacologiche Mario Negri (IRFMN) and Pintail (PT), however partners Fundacio Clinic per a La Recerca Biomedica (FCRB), Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Rennes (CHUR) and Institut National de Recherche Pour L'agriculture, L'alimentation et L'environnement (INRAE) also play an active role in this work package.

WP5 has four objectives:

1. To orchestrate and facilitate the progress of the project and all work packages and activities
2. To promote the aims and activities of the project (communication) and of its results (dissemination)
3. To identify, manage and protect new intellectual property and innovation
4. To prepare for the further development and exploitation of the project results.

The topic of this report is the Deliverable 5.5 *Updated Data Management Plan* (DMP) for which PT is the lead beneficiary. D5.5 relates to the following tasks, noting that these tasks span the duration of the project.

- Task 5.3 – Dissemination – good data management practice allows for the dissemination of the project results.
- Task 5.4 – Innovation Management – good data management enables the consortium to ensure data is appropriately managed in line with innovations discovered and developed within the project.
- Task 5.5 - Exploitation Planning – good data management ensures the exploitability of the results and in this case, swift progress to a clinical trial as is the goal of the project.

The management of ‘background’ of each partner brought to the project is covered in the signed PHOENIX Consortium Agreement, background being “*data, know-how or information (...) that is (...) needed to implement the Action or exploit the results*”. Further, the PHOENIX Consortium Agreement includes the clause ‘specific responsibilities regarding data protection’, whereby the partners’ responsibilities applicable under data protection laws are articulated. New beneficiary, INRAE, acceded to the Consortium Agreement on 22 July 2024.

3. Approach

As a reminder of process, the approach taken to develop the initial DMP and then this update is outlined below.

3.1 Initial DMP Development Process

The Initial PHOENIX Data Management Plan (D5.3) has been developed in the first six months of the project. The purpose of the Initial DMP was to ensure that the project is fully feasible and that the planned data management activities are underway. To this end, the Initial DMP was drafted by beneficiary Pintail, and via advice of the other partners (excluding INRAE at the time), building on the data management components included within the PHOENIX Grant Agreement.

The Initial DMP (and updated DMP) includes a summary of the data to be produced and managed during the course of PHOENIX and outlines:

- a summary of the data
- strategies that ensure the data complies with FAIR principles, the international standard of research data management
- the management of non-data-oriented research outputs
- allocation of resources to ensure sound data management
- data security and ethical issues, including compliance with GDPR, have been considered throughout the Initial DMP drafting process.

3.2 DMP - a Living Document

PHOENIX recognises the need to continuously consider data management within the project and thus the DMP is viewed as a living document and is now formally submitted as an update at M19 for D5.5. Updates are required when changes that meet the following, although not exhaustive, thresholds occur:

- the generation of new data (not foreseen in the DMP)
- changes in data access provisions or curation policies
- attainment of tasks (e.g., datasets deposited in a repository, etc.)
- changes in relevant practices (e.g., new innovation potential, decision to file for a patent)
- changes in consortium composition (as occurred via the introduction of INRAE).

4. Results – PHOENIX Updated Data Management Plan

4.1 Data Summary

New data generated within the PHOENIX project will include the following, data will be prepared and submitted in a form to facilitate re-use, complying entirely with the FAIR principles.

- Shared experimental data from laboratory research: phenotype, immunological function, transcriptomic, sex, weight, age, etc.
- Data collected in our planned murine and porcine studies and analysed in PHOENIX to assess the efficacy of the new nanomedicines.
- Single cell transcriptomic data, etc.
- Specifications for the pMHC-NP nanoparticle production (as ‘other’ research outputs)
- Experimental protocols (as ‘other’ research outputs)

Please refer to Appendix A for a more detailed summary of the data named above and to section 4.3 below for further details on other research outputs.

4.2 FAIR Data

In line with the FAIR principles, PHOENIX is committed to optimising the re-use of data generated withing the project.

The PHOENIX consortium has strong links with [Italian ELIXIR nodes](#) at the Universities of Padua and Milan (Bicocca), who are expert in [European Open Science Cloud](#) (EOSC) and will provide us with any external guidance needed to maximise the value of our data into the future. In line with their standard practice, IRFMN generated data will be stored in the [Zenodo](#) repository and FCRB generated data in secure cloud storage services, including One Drive, Sugar Synch, and iCloud. Cell lines are stored at the [IDIBAPS Biobank](#). CHUR data will be stored locally at CHUR in line with the local procedures, as well as in the PHOENIX project secure repository. In addition, INRAE will store, on its own secured servers, all the information related to the experimental pigs' identity and their individual characteristics (sex, weight, age, genitors' identity and lineage, treatments, sanitary status, *etc.*) according to EU and French legislation pertaining to establishments that produce and use experimental animals.

4.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Within PHOENIX, all publications will use persistent digital object identifier (DOI), and data will be stored on the EOSC, for maximum accessibility and findability. Further, PHOENIX will apply standardised metadata, terminologies and ontologies (e.g., [MedDRA](#), [OGMS](#), [ICD](#)), to simplify the location, interpretation and re-use of the data.

4.2.2 Making data accessible

In line with commitment to provide access to data, once Intellectual Property (IP) protection is complete, published experimental data will be made available to all bonafide researchers, under the [CC BY license model](#).

In line with the requirements of journals, raw data on transplant outcomes will be made available, for example transcriptomic datasets will be deposited in GEO and the accession codes, as provided in the papers, will be released once the respective paper is published.

In terms of the sharing of PHOENIX generated data to a third party, the process will include approval by the project principal investigators.

Data provided by a third party to PHOENIX will not be further shared.

4.2.3 Making data interoperable

To enable interoperability, data in PHOENIX will be prepared in standardised pre-clinical research formats such as the [CDISC Standard for the Exchange of Nonclinical Data](#) (CDISC-SEND), optimized for subsequent integration or transformation into other standard formats. As above, we will apply standardised metadata, terminologies and ontologies (e.g., [MedDRA](#), [OGMS](#), [ICD](#)), to simplify the location, interpretation and re-use of the data.

4.2.4 Increase data re-use

To increase the re-use of data outputs from PHOENIX, in line with the parameters outlined in section 4.2.2 above, data will be shared under the CC BY licence preferred by EOSC. The use of standard formats and ontologies means that many tools and utilities (both open-source and

proprietary) are already available for data processing and re-use. Curation and storage of the shared data will be the role of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

As a standard, the following documentation will accompany the data:

- Study protocol
- Reagent, technical and experimental metadata
- List of definitions
- Ethical approval application form
- Investigator sites information
- Insurance information
- Safety monitoring
- Database schema
- Data management plan

4.3 Other research outputs

In PHOENIX, in addition to new data, the following research outputs are also anticipated:

- Curation and Specifications for the pMHC-NP nanoparticle production
- Experimental protocols

4.4 Allocation of resources

Each research site (IRFMN, FCRB, CHUR, INRAE) will store and process the data in line with their organisational practices.

IRFMN data is on the local IRFMN server in Milan that fulfils IT system security requirements. FCRB store data in Cloud Services (iCloud, Google Drive, One Drive, Sugarsynch) and in Supercomputing Clusters, as well as in hard drives or NAS systems. CHUR data is on the local secure CHUR server in Rennes. INRAE data is on national secure INRAE servers.

As Principal Investigator, Prof. Giuseppe Remuzzi, is responsible for data management for the project overall, including, in partnership with Pintail, the implementation and updating of the DMP. In addition, principal investigators at each site (IRFMN, FCRB, CHUR, INRAE) will be responsible for the data management at that particular site, see table below.

Site	Lead investigator
ISTITUTO DI RICERCHE FARMACOLOGICHE MARIO NEGRI	Prof. Giuseppe Remuzzi
FUNDACIO CLINIC PER A LA RECERCA BIOMEDICA	Prof. Pere Santamaria
CENTRE HOSPITALIER UNIVERSITAIRE DE RENNES	Prof. Karim Boudjema
INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE POUR L'AGRICULTURE, L'ALIMENTATION ET L'ENVIRONNEMENT	David Val-Laillet

Data capture, including metadata, will be the responsibility of the principal investigator at each site and members of their associated research team.

This is a collaborative project with multiple partners involved, datasets will be openly shared among partners upon request, however, reside with the originating partner.

Each beneficiary is provided with sufficient person months within the project to deliver the tasks outlined above.

4.5 Data security

All data will be collected and stored in a secure fashion. IRFMN back up their data to an external server. FCRB back up data to external hard drives and/or cloud services (see section 4.4. above). CHUR back up data to external hard drives. INRAE back up data to an external server and external hard drives.

4.6 Ethics

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) is a strategic commitment of all four research partners, reflecting the emphasis placed on this by both the institutions themselves and by funding agencies and ethical review and approval bodies. We are committed to maintaining social values while delivering excellent science; this includes Ethics, and most notably in this project, animal welfare and the ['3Rs' of replacement, reduction, and refinement.](#)

Local ethics approval is being sought in the two sites where animal experiments will take place, namely: IRFMN – Italy (mice) and INRAE – France (pigs).

For pig experimentation in France, the Regional Ethics Committee in Animal Experiment of Brittany (CREEA) will be in charge of evaluating the entire procedure performed under the individual authorization of David VAL-LAILLET (n°35-88), before being definitely authorized by the French Ministry of Higher Education, Research and Innovation. All the animal experimentations will be performed at the INRAE UE3P, Unit of Pig Physiology and Phenotyping (Certification N° D35-275-32).

5. Impact and Conclusion

Completion of the updated data management plan is a key output for WP5 – Management, Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation. This DMP continues to provide guidance to each of the research sites as they progress through the experimental phases of the project.

6. Appendices

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Appendix A – Data Summary Details

Data Name	Format/Type	Purpose of Data (in relation to project objectives)	Expected size of the data	Data origin or provenance	Data utility (to whom is this data useful?)
Murine kidney graft function	Store in Excel spreadsheet/clinical data including animal sex, functional parameters, and graft outcomes	Assessing efficacy of nanoparticles	Data will be collected from more than 300 kidney transplanted mice	IRFMN	Basic and transplant immunologists
Murine liver graft function	Store in Excel spreadsheet/clinical data including animal sex, functional parameters, and graft outcomes	Assessing efficacy of nanoparticles	Data will be collected from more than 100 kidney transplanted mice	IRFMN	Basic and transplant immunologists
Phenotypic and function of pMHC-NP expanded cells	Store in Excel spreadsheet/phenotypic and functional data including FACS analysis, in-vivo test and in-vivo adoptive transfer experiments	Mechanism of action and characterization of the involved cellular network	Data will be collected from more than 100 mice	IRFMN/FCRB	Basic and transplant immunologists
Porcine liver graft function	CSV files and Excel spreadsheets including donor and recipient parameters, liver function tests and graft outcomes	Assessing efficacy of nanoparticles	Data will be collected from more than 20 recipients	CHUR/INRAE	Basic and transplant immunologists

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